

Sulphur Ligand Derivatives of Organo-silicon, -germanium, -tin, and -lead†

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A brief review of the organo-silicon, -germanium, -tin and -lead derivatives with a few selective ligands, e.g. thiols¹⁻³, dithiols⁴⁻¹⁰, dialkyldithiophosphates¹¹⁻¹⁶, alkylenedithiophosphates¹⁷⁻²², monothio- β -diketonates²³⁻²⁶, β -aminothionates²⁷, benzothiazolines²⁸⁻³⁰ and xanthates³¹, is being presented. The chemistry of these M-S-C derivatives has been compared with M-O-C derivatives like alkoxides³², glycoxides³³, β -diketonates³⁴ and carboxylates³⁵. Tin tetrathiolate-acetic anhydride reaction has been explored as a convenient route for the synthesis of tin tetracetate³⁴, which has been utilised as a starting material for the preparation of various sulphur ligand derivatives of tin³⁵. Work has been initiated on some other sulphur ligand derivatives like thiocarboxylates³⁶⁻³⁸ and dithiocarbamates³⁹⁻⁴² including monothiocarbamates^{43,44}.

Interest in the chemistry of sulphur ligand derivatives has been growing continuously and a few review articles⁴⁵⁻⁵⁴ published since 1981 are indicated. The main focus of attention in this presentation would be the derivatives of only a few ligands, on which work has been pursued in our laboratories.

Thiolato derivatives :

Thiol derivatives, $R_{4-n}M(SR')_n$ are the simplest metal sulphur compounds of main group elements (Si, Ge, Sn and Pb). These can be synthesised by the nucleophilic substitution at group IV metal sites by appropriate sulphur reagents¹⁻⁸.

(In a few cases, gaseous ammonia has also been used as hydrogen chloride acceptor)

($Mg(SR')_2$ and $Pb(SR')_2$ can be used in place of $NaSR'$)

The formation of compounds, $R_{4-n}M(SR')$ from their oxygen analogues or even from their oxides in some cases (Ge and Sn) becomes more facile with increasing atomic number of the central element ($Pd > Sn > Ge >> Si$). This tendency suggests a trend towards stronger π -bonding in the case of heavier metals. A comparative study of alcoholysis of tin, germanium and silicon mercaptides shows that only silicon derivatives are apparently reactive ; this can be easily understood to arise from the absence of effective $d\pi$ interaction in silicon. The class 'b' character of tin has been emphasized by Lappert⁵⁵ on chemical observations and thermochemical data. The comparative stability of tin-sulphur bond is further exhibited in the reactivity of even glycoxytin derivatives with thiols⁶,

The role of metal to ligand dative π -bonding is even more discernable in the case of transition metals. Whereas the mercaptides of later transition metals (Co, Ni, Cu, Pd and Ag) are quite easily formed and are stable like those of tin, mercaptides of earlier transition metals like Ti, Zr, Nb, appear to be extremely unstable ; the facile formation of stable $Cp_2Ti(SR)_2$ has, therefore, been ascribed due to enhanced electron density on titanium⁵⁶.

Following investigations on the nature of S-M bond by a variety of techniques (e.g., uv, ¹³C nmr, esca, dipole measurements, kinetic studies, ionisation energy measurements, kinetic studies, ionisation

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energy measurements, mass spectrometry, etc.), the same has been studied by X-ray diffraction technique⁶⁰. Studies of photoelectron spectra and of ionisation energies⁶¹ of R₃MSR' type derivatives have shown that the changes in the R' group from alkyl (e.g. methyl) to aryl (e.g. phenyl) do not, in spite of the differences in inductive effects, influence appreciably the extent of pπ-dπ interaction between S and R₃M group. Chemical reactivity as well as other physicochemical characteristics indicate that this pπ-dπ interaction between sulphur and metal is generally quite weak in all cases, and although small in magnitude, it appears to follow the trend, Pb > Sn > Ge > Si. The smallness of this interaction in the solid state also has been confirmed⁶² by X-ray analyses of the compounds, Ph₃MSMe (where, M=C, Si, Ge, Sn, Pb). In all cases, the central atom M exhibits a distorted tetrahedral coordination; only the propeller shape orientation of the phenyl rings appears to be affected by the changes in the electronic nature of the central atoms as well as by steric effects.

Quite a large number of derivatives of tin in particular with the substituted thiol ligands have been investigated during the last two decades. For example, a compound Me₂Sn(SCH₂CH₂)₂NMe, synthesised in our laboratories from facile reaction of Me₂Sn(OEt)₂ with MeN(CH₂CH₂SH)₂, has been recently recharacterised⁶³ by X-ray crystallography to be a pentacoordinated derivative, in which the less electronegative sulphur atoms are situated equatorially leaving a methyl group and the N-Sn bond in apical positions; the tin atom is 0.37 Å displaced out of the equatorial ring towards the apical methyl group (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Structure of Me₂Sn(SCH₂)₂NMe.

A detailed study of modes of coordination of 1,2-aminothiols in organotin(IV) complexes by ¹¹⁹Sn, ¹⁵N and ¹³C spectroscopy has been published recently⁶³.

Dithiolato-complexes :

The bridging tendency of the mercaptide groups is much lower than that of the alkoxy groups and this is depicted clearly in the monomeric behaviour⁶ of Sn(SR)₄ compared to oligomeric character of Sn(OR)₄ derivatives. The much weaker coordinative tendency of thiolate (SR) compared to alkoxy (OR) ligand is also reflected in the organometal dithiolates being in general unassociated (or at the most dimeric) cyclic species, compared to the corresponding glycoxytin⁶⁴ derivatives which are in general highly associated, non-volatile and often

insoluble products; the glycoxy analogues of organogermanium⁶⁵, however, are mostly monomeric, soluble and volatile.

The methods described for the synthesis of monothiolates are in general applicable for dithiolates also. Although there are many interesting publications, only three recent ones from the laboratories of Huber and Barbieri would be specifically mentioned here. Work on derivatives of 3,4-toluenedithiol (H₂TDT)⁶⁶, bis(triorganometal) and diorganometal-1,3-dithiolates, (R₃M)₂(C₆H₄XS₂) and R₂M(C₆H₄XS₂) (M=Sn, Pb; X=H, Cl)⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹ has been followed by that on organotin and organolead derivatives of 1,2-dimethyl-4,5-bis(mercaptomethyl)benzene (H₂DBB) and quinoxaline-2,3-dithiols (H₂QDT). Detailed ¹H nmr and Mössbauer spectroscopic studies⁶⁹ on these derivatives indicate pentacoordination of tin in R₂SnTDT and its tetracoordination in Me₂SnDBB, (R₂Sn)₂DBB (R=Me, Ph) and (Ph₂Sn)₂TDT.

An interesting series of thio-chelates of germanium and tin(M) have been described by simple thiolysis reactions of the type^{6,70},

All the germanium derivatives (I, II, III and IV) and even the mixed derivatives (V and VI) are volatile and monomeric. The dibutyltin derivative(I) of 2-mercaptoethanol is dimeric and distills at 194° under 1.5 mm (whereas the monomeric germanium

analogue distils at 95° under 1.5 mm). The Sn derivative appears to have the structure (Fig. 2),

Fig. 2

It may be appropriate to mention that the reactions of tetraisopropoxides, $\text{M}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ with 2(or>2) moles of 2-mercaptoethanol yield products of the composition $\text{M}(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2$. Out of these, $\text{Ge}(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2$ can be recrystallised from benzene and is monomeric^{7,1}, but the tin derivative $\text{Sn}(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})_2$ is an insoluble white solid. Even more interesting is the finding that in 1 : 1 molar reaction, instead of the mixed derivative, $\text{M}(\text{OPr}^i)_2(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{S})_2$, the products isolated correspond in analysis to $\text{M}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{S})_2$ in 50% yield,

This shows the stability conferred on the product as a result of chelate formation; these results are in sharp contrast with the corresponding reactions with glycols in which mixed products are obtained^{7,2,7,8} as represented by the equation,

In another comparative study, dithiol and diol derivatives of dialkyltin have been synthesised by the reactions,

The derivatives VII (R = Me, Bu) are colourless volatile low melting solids/liquids, whereas other products (VIII and IX) are cyclic white crystalline solids which are monomeric in benzene.

Dialkyl- and alkylene-dithiophosphates :

Dialkyldithiophosphoric acids (which can be easily prepared by the reactions of P_4S_{10} with alcohols) and their esters have found wide applications in the post-war years as pesticides under trade names such as ethion, malathion and thimet. The extraordinary biocidal activity of organotin dialkyldithiophosphates (much higher than that computed on the basis of the two main components) has aroused considerable interest in their synthesis and structural aspects in recent years particularly in the schools of Mehrotra¹¹⁻¹⁶ and Zuckerman^{7,4-8,1}. In continuation of their earlier work on dialkyldithiophosphates, Mehrotra and coworkers have

Table 1

I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	XV	XVI	XVII	XVIII
1 H																	2 He
3 Li ^b	4 Be											5 B	6 C	7 N	8 O	9 F	10 Ne
11 Na ^b	12 Mg ^b											13 Al ^a	14 Si ^a	15 P	16 S	17 Cl	18 Ar
19 K ^b	20 Ca ^b	21 Sc	22 Ti ^a	23 V ^b	24 Cr ^b	25 Mn ^b	26 Fe ^b	27 Co ^b	28 Ni ^b	29 Cu ^b	30 Zn ^b	31 Ga ^b	32 Ge ^a	33 As ^b	34 Se ^b	35 Br	36 Kr
37 Rb ^b	38 Sr	39 Y	40 Zr ^a	41 Nb ^a	42 Mo ^a	43 Tc	44 Ru ^a	45 Rh ^a	46 Pd ^a	47 Ag ^a	48 Cd ^a	49 In ^b	50 Sn ^b	51 Sb ^b	52 Te ^b	53 I	54 Xe
55 Cs ^a	56 Ba ^b	57-71 Ln [*]	72 Hf	73 Ta	74 W ^b	75 Re	76 Os	77 Ir ^b	78 Pt ^b	79 Au ^b	80 Hg ^b	81 Tl ^b	82 Pb ^b	83 Bi ^b	84 Po	85 At	86 Rn
87 Fr	88 Ra	89-103 Ac ^{**}	104 Unq	105 Unp	106 Unh	107 Uns											

^aNot fully characterised, or reported in the patent literature only. ^bCharacterised well.

recently initiated studies on alkylene dithiophosphates of main group IV element¹⁷⁻²² extending the same for comparison to some group III (Ga³⁺, In³⁺, Tl³⁺) and group V (As⁵⁺, Sb⁵⁺, Bi⁵⁺) elements as well as to nickel²³ and rhodium²⁰.

The enclosed periodic table (Table 1) depicts the breadth of interest in dialkyldithiophosphate chemistry of various metals. In the following equations are summarised the reactions generally employed for the synthesis of organo-germanium and -tin dialkyldithiophosphates,

(R = CH₃, C₂H₅, n-C₄H₉ and C₆H₅; R' = C₂H₅, n-C₂H₇, i-C₃H₇ and C₆H₅; n = 1-3).

It has been reported¹⁷⁻²² that the corresponding organo-germanium and -tin derivatives of alkylene dithiophosphoric acids can be synthesised by similar methods.

Eremeeva and Vorsina²¹ and Lefferts *et al.*²⁶ have described the synthesis of compounds of the type Sn[S₂P(OR)₂]₂ by the following reactions,

Similar methods have been employed for the synthesis of lead(II)^{23,25} and organolead(IV)²⁴ dialkyldithiophosphates. Et₂SnS₂P(OEt)₂ could be converted into Et₂GeS₂P(OEt)₂ or vice versa by appropriate reactions with Et₂GeCl or Et₂SnCl. Similarly, Et₂SiS₂P(OEt)₂ could be converted into the corresponding organo-germanium(IV) and -tin(IV) derivatives²⁵.

The properties of dialkyl and alkylene dithiophosphates of main group IV elements show gradation of the expected type. Organo-silicon(IV), -germanium(IV), -tin(IV) and -lead(IV) derivatives show monomeric behaviour in solution. Derivatives of the former two elements are generally liquids (at ambient temperatures) which can be volatilised under reduced pressure, but most of the organotin(IV) and almost all organolead(IV) derivatives are solids with sharp melting points. Trialkyl- and dialkyltin(IV) derivatives can also be volatilised but the monoalkyltin and all organolead analogues tend to decompose when attempts are made to volatilise these.

Structural aspects: Dialkyl- and alkylene-thiophosphato moieties can bind the metal in a variety of ways as depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Structural possibilities of dialkyl- and alkylene-dithiophosphates.

In actual experience also the dithiophosphate derivatives of metals of all the above types have been identified. Whereas strongly electropositive alkali metal and ammonium derivatives belong to category A, Te(S₂P(OCH₃)₂)₂ represents truly unidentate type²⁶. Ni[S₂P(OCH₃)₂]₂²⁷ and Cu₄[S₂P(OC₂H₅)₂]₄²⁸ can be cited as examples of bidentate and bridging types, respectively. Dialkyldithiophosphates behave more generally as bidentate ligands, especially with transition metals, and till recently, the only example²⁹ of a unibonded derivative was the 2,9-dimethyl-1,10-phenanthroline adduct of Ni[S₂P(OCH₃)₂]₂; a more detailed physicochemical study of the above and other similar nickel and palladium products has recently been carried out in our laboratories³⁰. In the case of organotin derivatives, Mehrotra and coworkers were the first to suggest the monodentate¹¹ and anisobidentate¹² nature of bonding in triorgano- and diorgano-tin dialkyldithiophosphates, respectively, on the basis of spectroscopic evidence. These conclusions have been almost simultaneously confirmed by X-ray crystallographic analysis of Ph₂Sn[S₂P(OEt)₂] as well as of Ph₂Sn(S₂POCH₂CMe₂CH₂O)¹⁰⁰ and of Ph₂Sn[S₂P(OEt)₂]₂ as well as of Me₂Sn(S₂POCMe₂CMe₂O)¹⁰¹. From an analysis of proton decoupled ³¹P nmr data for a large number of derivatives, Glidewell¹⁰² had concluded that ³¹P-chemical shift could be expected in the regions, 101-107, ~82 and 88-101 ppm for bonding modes A, B and C, respectively. Doubts have been raised¹² for the universality of the above generalisation and, therefore, efforts should always be made to confirm the conclusion from such criteria by more reliable information such as Mössbauer spectroscopy (wherever applicable) and other nmr data.

Electronic spectra¹¹⁻¹⁴ of organo-silicon(IV), -germanium(IV) and -tin(IV) dialkyldithiophosphates show a broad strong band at ca. 224 nm, which has been assigned to interligand π-π* electronic transition. The ir and pmr data of dialkyldithiophosphates of different elements (including Si, Ge, Sn and Pb) have been tabulated in a recent review article¹⁵, but these data do not throw much definitive light on the nature of coordinate bond in these compounds.

¹¹⁹Sn nmr chemical shifts have been found to be influenced by changes in (i) the coordination number of tin, (ii) the bond angles at tin, (iii) the ππ-dπ bonding effect, or (iv) by the presence of electronegative substituents. ¹¹⁹Sn nmr spectral data have been reproduced (Table 2) from a recent

publication of Clark *et al.*¹⁶ for a few organotin(IV) dialkyldithiophosphates and a few other organotin compounds for comparison. It is apparent from the data in Table 2 and other more extensive physicochemical measurements¹⁰⁷ that for four-coordinated tin compounds, ¹¹⁹Sn nmr chemical shifts appear generally in a higher field region from SnMe₄, used as standard. As the coordination

TABLE 2—¹¹⁹Sn NMR CHEMICAL SHIFTS OF SOME ORGANOTIN(IV) COMPOUNDS IN CDCl₃ SOLUTIONS

Compd.	Coordination no.	δ (¹¹⁹ Sn)*
Me ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	107.9
Me ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	103.9
Et ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	105.9
Et ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	100.3
Pr ⁱ ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	97.1
Pr ⁱ ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	91.3
Bu ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	99.3
Me ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	-159.6
Me ₃ Sn[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	-162.2
MeSn[S ₂ P(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	-163.4
MeSn[S ₂ P(OPr ⁱ) ₂] ₂ ^a	—	-185.7
Me ₃ SnSMe ^b	4	90
Me ₃ Sn(SMe) ₂ ^b	4	144
[Bu ₃ Sn(OEt) ₂] ₂ ^c	5	-160
Me ₃ Sn[(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂] ₂ ^d	6	-336
PbSn(S ₂ CNEt ₂) ₂ ^e	7	-695

* In ppm downfield from external Me₄Sn(neat) standard; 10–15% sample (w/v) in CHCl₃, was used and spectra recorded at 22°. ^a Ref. 16. ^b Ref. 103. ^c Ref. 104. ^d Ref. 105. ^e Ref. 106.

number increases from 4 to 5 or 6 or 7, the tin signal gradually moves to lower field, e.g. 0 to -200 for five-, -125 to -365 for six-, and -400 to -700 ppm for seven-coordination compounds. The ¹¹⁹Sn nmr chemical shifts for R₃Sn[S₂P(OR')₂]₂ occur in the range δ 91–108, indicating four-coordination; substitution of Et, Prⁿ or Buⁿ groups for Me results in increased shielding for tin nucleus and lowering in the observed ¹¹⁹Sn value. The ¹¹⁹Sn nmr chemical shifts for R₂Sn[S₂P(OR')₂]₂ species fall in the range of -160 ppm; these values indicate weak six-coordination state for tin, which may be due to four-membered ring strain. For tris-derivatives, RSn[S₂P(OR')₂]₃, ¹¹⁹Sn values are -163.4 and -185.7 ppm which may indicate 5/6-coordination state for tin; this conclusion could not be verified by the appearance of two types of signals (due to single and bicoordinated moieties) in ³¹P nmr spectra, upto even as low a temperature as -90° in CD₂Cl₂. It has, therefore, been inferred that all the ligands are equivalent either due to a fast exchange in a lower (5/6) coordination state, or alternatively due to weak coordination of all the ligands to the central tin atom in seven-coordination species. Similar inference has been obtained by detailed ¹H, ¹³C and ³¹P nmr spectra of the compounds and these have been confirmed by Mössbauer studies of a few samples¹⁶.

Molloy and Zuckerman¹⁰⁸ have in a recent publication summarised the Mössbauer and X-ray

crystal structure data for a number of organotin-dialkyldithiophosphates. The crystal structures of a few characteristic species Ph₃Sn[S₂P(OEt)₂]₂¹⁰⁰, Ph₃Sn[S₂P(OEt)₂]₂¹⁰¹, Ph₃Sn[S₂P(OPrⁱ)₂]₂¹⁰⁰, Sn[S₂P(OC₆H₅)₂]₂⁷⁶, Ph₃Ge[S₂P(OMe)₂]₂¹⁰⁹, Ph₃Ge[S₂P(OMe)₂]₂¹⁰⁹, Ph₃Pb[S₂P(OEt)₂]₂¹¹⁰, Ph₃PbS-Ph¹¹⁰, Ph₃Pb[S₂P(OCH₂Ph)₂]₂¹¹⁰ and Ph[S₂P(OPrⁱ)₂]₂^{98,111}, and adducts of zinc¹¹², tin(II)⁷⁶ and lead(II)¹¹¹ dialkyldithiophosphates are in conformity with the principles indicated above.

In spite of lack of adequate structural data on the oxygen analogues of dialkyldithiophosphates, their low solubility and high m.p.'s themselves suggest^{77,78} much more associated structures, an inference which is corroborated by available structural information also. This is in line with the greater bridging tendency of alkoxy groups discussed in the section on thiolates also. Work on mixed O—S ligands also, initiated¹¹³ in 1975, should be a rich field for further investigations.

Monothio-β-diketonates and related derivatives :

Derivatives of a number of symmetrical as well as unsymmetrical monothio-β-diketones of organo-silicon, -germanium, -tin and -lead have been reported recently by Mehrotra *et al.*^{24-26,114}. The preparative routes for these derivatives may conveniently be depicted as shown below,

All the trialkyl-silicon and -germanium derivatives appear to be monomeric tetrahedral volatile products with unidentate ligand-metal bonding¹¹⁴ through sulphur atom. The trialkyltin derivatives are also monomeric in refluxing benzene. Spectral studies of tin derivatives indicate a distorted tetrahedral structure, with very weak interaction between the tin atom and oxygen of the carbonyl group. Mössbauer data also support the four-coordination state for tin atoms in these derivatives. However, it has been shown on the basis of observed lowering in ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=C} absorptions in their ir spectra that triorganolead derivatives are five-coordinated complexes¹¹⁴.

The chelating behaviour of the monothio-β-diketone ligands in diorganotin(IV) derivatives has been confirmed by the lowering of the absorptions due to ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=C} to 1558–1578 and 1490–1508 cm⁻¹, respectively. The observed coupling constants J–119 Sn–Me (80–82 Hz) in the

¹H nmr spectra of dimethyltin(IV) derivatives correspond to a distorted octahedral geometry. The Mössbauer spectra of a few diorganotin monothio-β-diketonates exhibit quadrupole splittings of the order of 3.14–3.20 mm s⁻¹, suggesting again a distorted octahedral structure (with C–Sn–C angles approximately 130°). Similarly, it has also been shown that diorganolead analogues are six-coordinated complexes²⁶. In case of monoorganotin(IV) monothio-β-diketonates the following structures (I to IV) have been proposed^{24–26} on the basis of physicochemical studies,

Recently, stepwise formation constants of the complexation of dialkyltin(IV) ions with monothio-dibenzoylmethane have been determined potentiometrically^{11,5}. It has been shown that the first formation constant increases with the change of alkyl group(R) from methyl to butyl in R₂Sn(IV), possibly due to an increase in the electrophilic character of tin with the length of the alkyl chain.

X-ray crystal structure of dimethyltin(IV)-bis(3-mercapto-1,3-diphenylprop-2-en-1-one) has been reported^{11,6}. Tin atom in this compound exhibits a strongly distorted octahedral environment with pairs of the same donor atoms (O and S) in *cis*-positions; the two methyl groups deviate significantly from the *trans*-positions, the C–Sn–C bond angle being 134.2°.

β-Aminothione derivatives of organotin(IV) have also been prepared by Mehrotra *et al.*^{27,28} using the following methods,

Completion of the above reactions were monitored with the help of ir studies²⁷. All these

products are soluble in common organic solvents and are monomeric in nature. Some of these are volatile under reduced pressure.

Mehrotra *et al.*^{27–29} have synthesised recently some organo-germanium and -tin(IV) derivatives of 2,2-disubstituted-benzothiazoline,

(M = Ge or Sn; R = Me, Et or Bu; R' = Me; R'' = Me, Et, Bu¹, or Ph)

On the basis of molecular weight, ir and pmr spectral data, five-coordination at both tin and germanium has been proposed for these complexes.

Xanthates :

Xanthate ions could be represented by the following canonical forms,

These resemble dithiocarbamate ligands in forming chelates with metal ions particularly in their higher coordination states^{9,11,7}. These usually function as bidentate ligands, chelating the central element or bridging two of them. This leads to structures ranging from monomeric and polymeric discrete molecules to infinite lattices. There is a growing interest in the chemistry of organotin(IV) xanthates^{9,11,7–12,5}. These derivatives could be prepared by the reactions of organotin(IV) chloride with potassium alkylxanthates in appropriate molar ratio,

Following the above route, Mehrotra *et al.*²⁸ reported also the synthesis of 1,3-dixanthatotetra-butyl-distannoxane derivatives,

Alternatively, the diorganotin(IV)-bis(xanthates) have also been prepared^{12,5} by the insertion of CS₂

across Sn—O bond in the corresponding diorganotin(IV) alkoxides,

Some derivatives of tri- and mono-organotin(IV) moieties have also been prepared by employing the above method. These organotin(IV) xanthate derivatives are generally liquids (except diphenyl- and dimethyl-bis-xanthates which are solids) are soluble in common organic solvents, and are monomeric in refluxing benzene. They tend to decompose on heating to the corresponding organotin(IV) sulphide,

Spectral studies (ir and nmr) have shown that the xanthate ligand behaves as bidentate in the case of tri- and di-organotin derivatives^{8,9,11,12,13}. It would be interesting to mention here that ¹¹⁹Sn nmr spectroscopy has indicated the tin atoms in the compounds Sn(exa)₂X₂ (where, exa = O-ethyl-xanthato; X = Cl, Br, I) to be hexacoordinated in dichloromethane solution^{12,13}. In addition to these, the compounds SnX(xan)₂ and SnX₂(xan) have also been characterised in solution by ¹¹⁹Sn nmr spectroscopy. Six- and four-coordinated structures have been suggested for SnBr(xan)₂ and SnBr₂(xan), respectively^{12,13}. However, these compounds could not be obtained in the solid state. In case of Me₂Sn(exa)₂, the position of ¹¹⁹Sn resonance indicates that this compound is four-coordinate in solution with 'exa' behaving as a monodentate ligand. However, its crystal structure shows a distorted octahedral environment about the tin atom in the solid state in which the chelating 'exa' ligands exhibit total asymmetry in their mode of coordination^{12,13}.

The application of ¹¹⁹Sn nmr spectral studies to the series R₂SnX(S₂COR') and R₂Sn(S₂COR')₂ (where, R = CH₃, C₆H₅; R' = C₂H₅, C₆H₇; X = Cl, Br, I) indicates that both types of compounds in solution have a coordination number less than six^{12,13}. The crystal structure of Ph₂SnCl(S₂COR) (where R = C₆H₅) shows that the tin atom is penta-coordinated in a distorted trigonal bipyramidal environment^{12,13}.

Conclusion :

The above brief account depicts some exciting developments in the sulphur ligand chemistry of main group IV metals in general, and of tin, in particular. Besides some fascinating revelations on the nature of M—S bonding, these derivatives have been proved to exhibit significant applications as biocides, etc. In spite of a very fast progress in the field, much more exciting chemistry is still expected to emerge from a comparative study of

metal—oxygen and metal—sulphur bonded derivatives, which are beginning to receive more concerted attention in our as well as other chemical laboratories around the world.

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